

D1.2 Data Management Plan (DMP)

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Deliverable Information sheet

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Executive summary

Management of data is an important element of large scale multi-disciplinary projects. As such, MARBEL will be collecting, using and generating a heterogeneous set of data throughout its lifecycle. This deliverable is the initial version of the project's Data Management Plan and explains the proposed actions for the overall control of MARBEL's data and publications. More specifically the following points are addressed:

- The guiding principles for data management in the project
- Data Summary, including an overview of what data will be gathered and processed in the project
- Provisions and principles for findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) Data Management
- Allocation of resources and the costs for data management in this project
- Provisions for data security as well as the adherence to the General Data Protection Directive (GDPR)
- Ethical aspects, the MARBEL privacy strategy as well as IPR issues.

The DMP provides a framework for good data handling by identifying the research data that the project expects to generate and describing which parts of the data can be shared with the public. Furthermore, it provides guidelines on naming conventions and metadata, storage of research data and steps to make them public available.

MARBEL will make use of open research data repositories such as Zenodo to comply with the Horizon 2020 Open Access policy. Public deliverables, publications and anonymized datasets will be made available with open access. Datasets generated by MARBEL will be given a persistent identifier (Digital Object Identifier, DOI), supplied with relevant metadata referencing the project name and grant agreement number. Ethical aspects related to data collection, generation and sharing will be considered for data collection, use and sharing. The DMP is a living document and will be periodically updated, as part of the project's periodic reports in order to reflect the actual research data generated during the project and include updated instructions on accessing open data.

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List of abbreviations

AI	<i>Artificial Intelligence</i>
BMS	<i>Battery Management System</i>
BP	<i>Battery Pack</i>
CA	<i>Consortium Agreement</i>
CE	<i>Circular Economy</i>
DMP	<i>Data Management Plan</i>
DOD	<i>Depth Of Discharge</i>
DOI	<i>Digital Object Identifiers</i>
EMC	<i>Electromagnetic Compatibility</i>
ECU	<i>Engine Control Unit</i>
EV	<i>Electric Vehicle</i>
eVIL	<i>Electric Vehicle In-the-Loop</i>
EU	<i>European Union</i>
FAIR	<i>Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable data</i>
ICO	<i>Information Commissioner's Office</i>
IPR	<i>Intellectual Property Rights</i>
GDPR	<i>General Data Protection Regulation</i>
KPI	<i>Key Performance Indicators</i>
MRL	<i>Manufacturing Readiness Level</i>
NDA	<i>Non-Disclosure Agreement</i>
OCV	<i>Open Circuit Voltage</i>
ORD	<i>Open Research Data</i>
PCB	<i>Printed Circuit Board</i>
RUL	<i>Remaining Useful Life</i>
SoC	<i>State of Charge</i>
SoH	<i>State of Health</i>
SoX	<i>State of X</i>
TRL	<i>Technology Readiness Level</i>
UFC	<i>Ultra-Fast Charging</i>
WLTC	<i>Worldwide Harmonized Light Vehicles Test Cycle</i>
WP	<i>Work Package</i>

1. INTRODUCTION

This document is the initial version of the MARBEL Data Management Plan and explains the proposed actions for the overall control of MARBEL's data and publications, a work performed within the WP1 Project Management and Task 1.3 Data requirements, planning and management. The DMP is a "living document" that will be constantly updated during the project and related updates will be included in the project's periodic technical reports.

In general, a Data Management Plan (DMP) is a key element of good data management as it describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed, and generated by a Horizon 2020 project. A main purpose of the DMP is to provide guidelines for making research data findable, accessible, interoperable, and re-usable (FAIR), and should include information on: (i) the handling of research data during and after the end of the project, (ii) what data will be collected, processed, and generated, (iii) which methodology and standards will be applied, (iv) whether data will be shared/made open access, and (v) how data will be curated and preserved (including after the end of the project). A DMP is required for all projects participating in the extended Open Research Data (ORD) pilot, including MARBEL.

The DMP described in this deliverable establishes the procedures on how to handle MARBEL data along the project and after its finalization. Hence, the document (and also the subsequent versions of it), represents the consortium agreements on the data plan and provides a description of the main datasets that will be used and produced as well as standards and methodologies that will be used for data collection, generation, sharing and preservation. Note that the MARBEL DMP has been created following the template provided by the European Commission on DMP structure and guidelines.

In order to derive datasets and data sources which will be used and created within the MARBEL project, a collaborative methodology was followed where all partners dealing with data were involved. A template to record existing and new datasets was created and was provided to relevant partners as an online document (google form). The template is provided in ANNEX I and includes information regarding the dataset's description, purpose and utility, reference and name, partner involved, format, related metadata and standards, license, relation to the project's objectives, whether it is a new or existing dataset and expected size. Partners were then asked to fill in the corresponding datasets. The outcome of this process was a record of existing and new datasets which are described in Sections 2.3.1 and 2.3.2 of this deliverable.

The remainder of the deliverable is structured as follows. In Section 2 the document embarks with a summarisation of the types and sources of data and continues in Section 3 with the description of the practices for safeguarding that the MARBEL research data are findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR). An account of the allocated resources for data management is included (Section 4). Then as an appreciation of the data security and ethical considerations, principles to be adopted is provided in Sections 5 and 6. The conclusions are part of Section 7.

2. DATA SUMMARY

2.1 Purpose of data collection

The main goal of MARBEL is to develop an innovative and competitive lightweight battery with the objective to accelerate the mass market take-up of electric and hybrid vehicles. MARBEL will design, develop and demonstrate a new compact, modular, weight-optimised and high-performance battery pack (BP) with longer life, greater energy efficiency in charging and energy use based on a robust and flexible battery management system (BMS) along with ultra-fast battery charging and cooling. Modularity will make possible to streamline repair, servicing and recycling processes, while preserving the value of new batteries and reducing hazards for operators and environmental impact. The data to be generated and used in the context of MARBEL contribute to the realization of the project's objectives.

For these purposes, MARBEL utilizes data that fall under two broad categories:

- a) **Primary data:** Primary data is the kind of data that is collected directly from the data source without going through any existing sources. In other words, these data will emerge from the MARBEL project and will be used to develop, test and fine tune the MARBEL BP as well as components that are required for its control (such as components for thermal and charging management as well as for estimating battery related parameters including State of Health (SoH), State of Charge (SoC), Remaining Useful Life (RUL) etc.). These may include data derived from the tests that will be executed in the labs, and data derived from the BMS, at the operational phase.
- b) **Secondary data:** Secondary data refers to data that has been collected in the past by someone else but made available for others to use. In other words, these data are already available and will be used for developing the MARBEL BP and related components and models, such as predictive models for SoH, SoC, RUL estimation. These may include existing data from previous related tests in the lab, and datasets from open databases.

Figure 1 provides an overview of the project's scope and the steps that will followed in order to develop the MARBEL battery focusing on the following main areas:

1. Advanced battery packaging using a Design for Assembly (DfA) and Disassembly (DfD) methodology. MARBEL follow a Design for Disassembly (DfD) methodology for BPs ready for 2nd use and dismantling, contributing to implementation of Circular Economy (CE) concepts.
2. Lightweight and sustainable Battery Packaging. MARBEL will provide an optimized cost-effective modular housing based on Recycled Aluminium Extruded Profiles, using innovative simulation techniques to optimize the material quantity for the housing.
3. Solutions and processes for the sustainable dismantling and 2nd life. MARBEL will provide a testing and classification standard development for used batteries which will be used for identifying and determining batteries' suitability for 2nd life applications.
4. Flexible advanced battery management systems. MARBEL will develop a BMS that is not tailored to any specific battery; in contrast, the proposed approach can be adapted to a large variety of batteries with minor changes based on firmware updates that can be done remotely if necessary in order to adapt to other applications and 2nd life use. The BMS will be able to gather battery sensor data through a wireless system with secure communications. The BMS will also incorporate methods and algorithms for State of X (SoX) estimation. Data mining approaches will be developed using multiple sources (partners' sources, public sources and other databases) and integrated in a data-driven Artificial Intelligence (AI) expert system, able to trigger alarms when early failure is detected and warn the EV user before any major problem happens.
- 5- Ultra Fast Charging strategies and enhanced thermal management. MARBEL aims to make use of Ultra-fast charging (UFC) and Extra Fast Charging (XFC) charging strategies in order to

allow longer trips with electric vehicles (EVs) while reducing drivers' "range anxiety" which is often pointed to as one of the key reasons why consumers haven't adopted battery-powered EVs yet.

6. Future performance & safety-related test procedures. MARBEL aims to improve state-of-the-art test procedures reducing time and cost while improving the quality and quantity of knowledge gathered about different systems.

7. BP validation under realistic conditions. MARBEL aims to reduce the need for real driving tests which are a lengthy and costly processes by developing an innovative concept of electric Vehicle-In-the-Loop (eVIL) for BP testing.

Figure 1: The scope of the MARBEL project. Different datasets will be used for the various steps that are required in order to develop the MARBEL BP.

2.2 Relation of Data to the Project's Objectives

In this Section, we present the relation of the already identified data to the project's objectives. More specifically the project objectives are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: MARBEL Project Objectives

Scientific and Technological objectives
SO1: Increase the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of MARBEL novel concepts to TRL 7-8
SO2: Reduce >20.6% the weight of BP systems ensuring all required safety and performance targets
SO3: Increase useful battery life of batteries to minimum of 300,000 km
SO4: Reduce 25 % the charging time of BPs and increase fast-charging repetitiveness
SO5: Develop sensors, secure communications and enhance predictive maintenance
Operational and business Objectives

SO6: Increase the Manufacturing Readiness Level (MRL) of new BP concepts by allowing large scale manufacturing, assembly, dismantling, safety and reconditioning by design
SO7: Ensure time/cost reduction at all levels, from BP design to dismantling and reconditioning processes
Policy and societal Social objectives
SO8: Meet CE goals by minimum 40% Life Cycle Analysis improvement by using modularity, ecodesign of BPs and flexible BMS, thus reducing environmental impact in all life cycle stages
SO9: Retrieve European industrial and social leadership at BP by becoming the future market standard
Policy and societal Social objectives
SO10: Meet CE goals by minimum 40% Life Cycle Analysis improvement by using modularity, ecodesign of BPs and flexible BMS, thus reducing environmental impact in all life cycle stages
SO11: Retrieve European industrial and social leadership at BP by becoming the future market standard

In terms of data, we have identified a set of main data categories which are relevant for the MARBEL project in Table 2 where their relevancy to the project objectives is also shown.

Table 2: Main data categories of the MARBEL Project and relation to the Project objectives.

Data Category	Relevant Objectives
Already available data from databases including battery tests containing data about life-cycle tests, standard cycling, fast charging etc.	SO1, SO3, SO5, SO6, SO7, SO9, SO10
Data from standard cycling tests of the cells under different temperatures and C-rates	SO1, SO3, SO5, SO6, SO7
Data emerging from characterization tests such as: internal resistance pulse tests @ different SoC levels, temperatures as well as C-rates, open circuit voltage (OCV) determination together with capacity validation, capacity tests at different C-rates, Worldwide Harmonized Light Vehicles Test Cycle (WLTC) tests and thermal measurements such as calorimetric experiments.	SO1, SO3, SO5, SO6, SO7, SO9
Data emerging from subassembly tests that will mainly contain components related to the cooling system: cooling plates, cooling pipes, valves, sensors, pump, etc.).	SO1, SO2, SO3, SO6, SO7
Data emerging from from tests at eVIL test bench	SO1, SO3, SO6, SO11
Data emerging from tests with the mini BP housing. It will mainly contain information about the mechanical behavior of the housing, but also pressure/force values and (if included) data from cell behavior (electrical behavior while deformation).	SO2, SO9
Dataset generated from the cell datasheet, showing the most basic characteristics of the cells.	SO2, SO4, SO9
Economic and environmental assessment data.	SO8, SO10
Dissemination material (including social media posts/press releases), scientific journal and conferences publications.	SO11

2.3 Types and formats of the project's data

In this Section, we present the already identified datasets of the MARBEL project. We classified these datasets in primary and secondary datasets. In the context of MARBEL, **primary datasets** are distinguished into two broad categories: (i) data derived from the tests that will be executed in the labs; and, (ii) data derived from the BMS, at the operational phase. On the other hand, **secondary datasets** are distinguished in the following broad categories: (i) existing data from previous related tests in the lab; and, (ii) datasets from open databases.

2.3.1 Primary datasets

Data set name	iSCM_data
Dataset description	The dataset includes temperature, voltage, current, SoC, balancing thresholds, standard cycling, etc.
Data source	experimental test
Testing procedure	Tests with purpose to acquire data in real-time from the battery and to send them wirelessly to BMS. These experiments will help to implement passive balancing.
Relevant Task	Task 4.3
Expected to become available	2022
Purpose – data utility	The dataset will be used for active and passive balancing, SoC estimation, development of battery management model, 2nd life estimation, optimization of payload size for wireless communication, data reliability, predictive maintenance, RUL estimation, fault diagnosis, etc. In this way, it will contribute to the development of solutions adaptable to different kinds of cells, electro-chemistries, and vehicles and will facilitate repairability and 2nd life transition. It will also contribute to the development of a flexible BMS that will result, among others, in the reduction of environmental impact in the lifecycle stages.
File format	CSV
Data sharing plan	Open
Expected size	data from ~100 tests

Data set name	Asymmetric Thermal Modulation for UFC cell
Dataset description	Test for determining the usefulness of the UFC approach proposed during the project proposal for enhancing the velocity of charge of EVs whilst trying to reduce the deterioration of them.
Data source	Cell tests: Data from lab about temperatures and charging status. eVIL Tests: UFC data
Testing procedure	Tests in order to heat/cool the battery implementing also fast charging.
Relevant Task	Task 3.1
Expected to become available	2021
Purpose – data utility	This test is the first validation of an unconventional Ultra-Fast Charge approach aiming at contributing to the increase of battery life, the reduction of the charging time of BPs and to the increase of fast-charging repetitiveness. Drawbacks of the proposed method are aimed to be found during the test.
File format	CSV

Data sharing plan	Closed: Related with cell behaviour
Expected size	100MB

Data set name	2nd life test
Dataset description	Test aged batteries with 2nd life power profiles
Data source	Experimental test (cyclor)
Testing procedure	Cycling of the cells in order to receive data for further analysis.
Relevant Task	Task 7.5
Expected to become available	2023
Purpose – data utility	The dataset will contribute to the Life Cycle Analysis (LCA) improvement by feeding into models that will extend the battery lifetime and the 2nd life operation.
File format	to be defined
Data sharing plan	to be defined
Expected size	to be defined

Data set name	Cell measurement data
Dataset description	<p>Dataset from initial cell tests will include standard cycling of the cells under different temperatures and C-rates, characterization tests such as internal resistance pulse tests at different SoC levels, temperatures as well as C-rates, OCV-determination together with capacity validation, capacity tests at different C-rates, WLTC-cycle tests and thermal measurements such as calorimetric experiments.</p> <p>The main recorded values will be: time, voltage, current, temperature, maybe visual data from a video camera / thermal camera.</p>
Data source	The data will come from experimental data at the start of testing, after we received the cells. A cyclor and a temperature chamber will be used to test and collect the data.
Testing procedure	Implementation of standard cycling to the cells under different temperatures (low temperature, room-temperature and elevated temperature ~40 °C) and C-rates (1, 2 and 3 C which are going to be defined after we received the cell datasheet). Moreover will take place characterization tests such as: internal resistance pulse tests at different SoC levels (100 % - 10 %), temperatures (see dataset description) as well as C-rates (charge and discharge direction, 1, 2 and 3 C), OCV-determination together with capacity validation (measured at 1/20 C), capacity tests at different C-rates (1, 2 and 3 C), WLTC-cycle tests and thermal measurements such as calorimetric experiments. Finally will be included tests related to ultra fast charging (yet to be defined, but probably high C-rate charging at an elevated temperatura (see fast charging approach).
Relevant Task	Tasks 3.1, 7.1, 7.2
Expected to become available	first datasets will be available around September 2021 (this is the estimated cell delivery time)

Purpose – data utility	The dataset will be used for modelling purposes (thermal, electrical, BMS algorithm) but also for feeding into the AI model and building a database for predicting life expectancy of the cells and to develop new testing methods. The cell test data will be a base for further investigations related to the system (from an experimental point of view). It will be used to predict lifetime of the cells, gather first impressions of their performance, act as a proof that the cells were chosen thoroughly according to the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) and the targeted safety and performance requirements. Moreover will the dataset act as one of the first inputs to the knowledge database / AI model in order to improve the whole testing procedures/action to facilitate it in the future. In this way, it will contribute to the increase of useful battery life, to the reduction of the charging time of BPs and to the increase of fast-charging repetitiveness.
File format	format will be mainly .csv/.xlsx . it will be timeline data, showing the time evolution of the abovementioned values/parameters.
Data sharing plan	from the state right now it will be open and submitted to a cloud (within the project).
Expected size	depending on the data record interval and the total test duration, between 100 - 500 MB (initial cell testing will in total take around 9 months, with about 1000 cycles to execute with the cells and interim characterization tests (5 tests with different duration, 140 h in total for the characterization). The plan is to cycle the cells, do the characterization, cycle again and so on. The number of cycles between the characterizations varies depending on the cycling C-rate between 10, 25 and around 50-100).

Data set name	Dataset from BMS tests
Dataset description	This dataset will be created from subtests, that are executed only with parts of the BMS for functional performance/safety purposes. In this dataset, no information about the cell behavior (electrical behavior) will be included, only information about reaction/behavior of the BMS and its peripherals.
Data source	Dataset will be generated by experimental tests with the BMS system and parts of it.
Testing procedure	Tests will provide data from sensor failure, actuator behavior in case of malfunctions, signalling/warning strategies, brown-out/black-out behavior, voltage drift of cells (can be simulated without the use of cells), short circuit of Printed Circuit Board (PCB) parts, behavior in case of simulated external requests (e.g. communicated requests via interface to "rest-of-vehicle") and switch to 2nd-Life application test.
Relevant Task	Task 7.3
Expected to become available	towards end of 2022
Purpose – data utility	The utility of data is to validate the correct behavior of the BMS in terms of performance and safety in first- and second-life applications. The flexible BMS will contribute to a high TRL, since it is capable of being used in a variety of applications. Moreover 2nd-Life transition will be way facilitated, since no new/different BMS will be needed and the whole information about the previous system can be used. The dataset also will help to prove that the BMS is adaptable to different applications/architectures. Finally, it will show if the developed sensors/communications and methods related to the BMS are behaving/working as expected.
File format	Some sort of report, simple table with "triggering event" and "reaction". Can be in a word-format or pdf, or powerpoint slides.
Data sharing plan	open
Expected size	5-10 MB

Data set name	Dataset from cooling system test
Dataset description	The dataset will contain information from subassembly tests that will mainly contain components related to the cooling system: cooling plates, cooling pipes, valves, sensors, pump, etc.). The tests are intended to show the efficiency, behavior and/or problems with the cooling system in terms of pressure drop, heat exchange, system control and sensor information. The tests will be outside of eVIL at this stage.
Data source	Dataset will be generated from experimental tests.
Testing procedure	Tests will include heat exchange with cooling plates, pressure drop measurements with given setup, general performance tests of the cooling system components and behavior in case of sensor failure/false measurement values.
Relevant Task	Task 7.3
Expected to become available	2022, depending on development state of cooling system
Purpose – data utility	The dataset will be useful for thermal management, modelling of the thermal behavior/system response, but also for a "proof-of-concept". Novel cooling concepts shall be tested and introduced to the thermal management. It is relevant for these objectives, since it will demonstrate what improvement the cooling concept brings in terms of performance, but also reveals weak points and/or drawbacks of the approach. Therefore, it helps to constantly improve the system. Additionally, the dataset will reveal the use of the sensors in the system and will help to optimize the reaction-chain between "sensor-value", "processing", "action".
File format	.csv-format from measurements
Data sharing plan	to be defined
Expected size	data from around 5-10 tests, dataset will contain data in the time domain (pressure, temperature, flow-rate, etc.)

Data set name	Dataset from module/BP tests outside of eVIL
Dataset description	This dataset will be created during multiple tests, that will be executed either with cyclers in the lab and temperature chamber or in an abuse area. Datasets will contain different information of the system/subsystems, including: time, voltage, current, temperature, sensor values, warning signals (from BMS), actuator states (e.g. cooling valves, main contactors), raw data communication (e.g. single cell voltages, balancing requests etc.). The information will be mainly limited by the system borders, meaning there is no information about interaction to external systems (like it will be in the eVIL).
Data source	dataset created through experimental tests in the lab and/or abuse area
Testing procedure	Implementation of performance tests like standard cycling, internal resistance measurements, impedance spectroscopy, cold cranking, high power discharge, high power charge, pulse/peak power/peak current tests, capacity validation, energy efficiency, drive cycle, thermal tests (this time with cells attached to the system) at module and pack level. Module level will differ in terms of gathered information, because there won't be a complete "picture" of the interaction within the whole system. Will be executed also Electromagnetic Compatibility (EMC) tests and safety tests including abusive tests like overcharging, deep discharging, short circuiting, fuel fire, crush (at module level), vibrational testing, temperature shock, overheating, thermal propagation. Finally Will be tested BMS-functionality with real cells attached to the BMS.

Relevant Task	Task 7.3
Expected to become available	from end of 2022
Purpose – data utility	Main purpose of the dataset is the validation and the testing of the concepts as well as the design of iterations if needed. Moreover it will prove the maturity of applied concepts and meanwhile help to further improve the processes including testing (since it will also feed the knowledge base and act as input to the AI model/processing).
File format	mainly .csv-format
Data sharing plan	open, but a limitation might be the data revealing cell behavior (restrictions regarding dissemination due to Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA))
Expected size	depending on the test duration and data recording approx. between 10 - 150 MB

Data set name	Dataset from BP tests at eVIL level
Dataset description	This dataset will contain information from tests at the eVIL. The character of the data will be more "close-to-reality", because it will include interaction information between the MARBEL system and external systems like power-electronics, motors, cooling peripherals, data systems, external boardnet components. The focus here is more towards the overall behavior of the MARBEL BP in a real driving situation in terms of performance, safety and interaction with the "rest-of-vehicle".
Data source	dataset from tests at eVIL test bench
Testing procedure	The testing procedure contains interaction of the system with external components such as charger, cooling peripherals, Engine Control Units (ECUs), motors, inverters. In general it refers to integration into "foreign" environment. Moreover real world tests with simulated temperature conditions and representative cycles (e.g. WLTC) and will be tested the condition of fast charging inside the eVIL. Finally will be examined communication, security and vulnerability assessment for external interfaces and robustness.
Relevant Task	Task 7.3
Expected to become available	end of 2023
Purpose – data utility	The main purpose is testing and validating the overall concept, integration into vehicle-like environment and check for design flaws. This dataset will act as a proof for a high TRL of the system, since it will demonstrate the modularity, integrability and behavior in a real-world-scenario. The concept of testing (eVIL concept) will contribute to save time and costs during testing phase. The dataset will on one hand demonstrate that, but also contribute to further improve the processes (MARBEL testing strategy). By demonstrating that novel test environment, this will serve as a public demonstrator on how to improve the test process in future developments, which is often neglected or of lower priority.
File format	probably .csv or some sort of table data. Depending on the test maybe also a report.
Data sharing plan	open, but same restrictions apply like in the non-eVIL tests regarding cell-information (NDA)
Expected size	depending on the test and amount of recorded values, between 5 - 150 MB

Data set name	Dataset from tests with mini BP (housing)
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Dataset description	This dataset will be generated when performing tests with the mini BP housing. It will mainly contain information about the mechanical behavior of the housing, but also pressure and force values and (if included) data from cell behavior (electrical behavior while deformation).
Data source	Dataset originates from experimental tests such as crush with the housing, deformation, drop tests, mainly focused on mechanical properties of the housing in order to get information that can be used for simulations.
Testing procedure	Testing procedure contains crush tests, impact tests, vibration tests, drop tests and acceleration tests.
Relevant Task	Task 7.3
Expected to become available	2023
Purpose – data utility	The dataset will contribute to modelling purposes and will be a proof of design and housing concept. Additionally the dataset will act as summary about how the pack might behave in hazardous or abnormal situations or just when big forces are applied to it. Thus, it will demonstrate the design intentions in order to reduce weight but meanwhile ensuring a high safety level. The intention of the tests is to save costs and time as well during testing, since experiments will be executed at a much smaller scale. Moreover will it help to perform tests at a very early stage, where design flaws and improvements can be identified.
File format	test report (e.g. .pdf or powerpoint) and/or .csv-files with the recorded data. Video files might also be included when recording during testing.
Data sharing plan	open
Expected size	depending on recorded data either around 100 MB (only measurement data), but if videos will be recorded files might be way bigger (even ~GB). Number of tests will be between approx. 5-10

Data set name	Life Cycle Inventory (LCI)
Dataset description	This dataset will contain inventory of input and output flows for the battery pack system. Such flows will include inputs of water, energy, and raw materials, and releases to air, land, and water. The inventory will be derived from data coming from technical actions and provided by all partners.
Data source	The dataset originates from experimental procedures, test labs.
Testing procedure	N/A
Relevant Task	Tasks 8.1,8.2,8.3
Expected to become available	It will be continuously improved during project execution until the end
Purpose – data utility	The main purpose of the dataset is to determine the economic and environmental impact in all life cycle stages of the solutions in order to improve LCA by using modularity, ecodesign of battery packs and flexible BMS and thus, to meet the circular economy goals. The dataset will feed into the impact model in order to demonstrate how these objectives are accomplished.
File format	Mainly *.xlsx
Data sharing plan	As a first term, it will be closed.
Expected size	2 datasets (economic and environmental) <= 5 MB

Data set name	Economic assessment
Dataset description	This dataset contains data regarding the life cycle costs associated to the MARBEL's proposed battery, including the whole battery pack system

	(modules and cells pack, housing, control modules and BMS,..) (raw materials and production of the components and their assembly), operational costs, end of life (recycling, disassembling,...) costs
Data source	The data will be obtained from the different partners in the consortium.
Testing procedure	The testing procedure contains production of the battery and assembling, energy consumption during the operational phase in the vehicle, considering the performance of the battery from the ageing tests, data from the experimental recycling.
Relevant Task	Tasks 8.2, 8.3, 8.4
Expected to become available	At the end of the project
Purpose – data utility	The main purpose of the dataset is to provide information about the costs of the MARBEL battery and to contribute to the time/cost reduction at all levels, from battery pack design to dismantling and reconditioning processes. This dataset will allow the comparison of the MARBEL battery economic performance with current LIB and demonstrate the cost reduction of the MARBEL's design
File format	.xml
Data sharing plan	Not defined yet, though the dataset will be owned by the MARBEL consortium
Expected size	<< 100Mb

Data set name	cellECTmodel
Dataset description	This dataset contains data for electrochemical and thermal modelling and simulation at cell level.
Data source	The input data for the simulations will come from the cell manufacturer
Testing procedure	The testing procedure contains laboratory tests that will be used to validate and modify the models.
Relevant Task	T3.1
Expected to become available	Depending on when the cells will become available
Purpose – data utility	The results of this modelling and simulation will be used at the next level (module) to continue with the design and to enable the development of solutions adaptable to various kinds of cells, electro-chemistries, vehicles, automotive segments, and OEMs. Setting up a model which will be validated will make it easier for future cells to be modelled.
File format	To be defined
Data sharing plan	It will be of internal use, as this dataset will be used at the battery pack level
Expected size	To be defined

2.3.2 Secondary datasets

Data set name	Cell datasheet
Dataset description	Dataset generated from the cell datasheet, showing the most basic characteristics of the cells. The data already exist at the cell manufacturer and will be provided to the Project.
Data source	Cell manufacturer will provide cell datasheet(s) with regular characteristics and safety datasheet.
Relevant Task	Task 3.1

Purpose – data utility	Getting a first impression of the main cell characteristics, will help to align the initial test procedures accordingly, take first architectural decisions (module design, safety limits etc.) and most important take measures with purpose to make all processes that include handling the cells in any manner safe. It is relevant to the objectives, because firstly the cell will contribute strongly to weight reduction (high energy density) but must definitely ensure safe operation. This information will also be taken out of the safety datasheet (are the cells safe to handle? will any toxic substances be released in case of damage? What must be taken care of during handling/manufacturing/testing? etc.). Hence, this information must be collected to ensure the safety of all involved parties. Additionally it is connected to reparability and 2nd-Life transition. This is somehow related to the reason that it involves processes where a handling of the cells is needed. Any useful data coming from the cell datasheet provided by the manufacturer is of use. Finally, BP design, dismantling and other reconditioning processes are directly linked to the cells, since they will steer and influence design processes and decisions.
File format	simple table in pdf or word-format that is extracted from cell datasheet(s)
Data sharing plan	not public
Expected size	low size, approx. < 5 MB

Data set name	Center for Advanced Life Cycle Engineering (CALCE) battery team
Dataset description	We provide open access to our experimental test data on lithium-ion batteries, which includes continuous full and partial cycling, storage, dynamic driving profiles, OCV measurements, and impedance measurements.
Data source	https://calce.umd.edu/battery-data
Relevant Task	Tasks 3.1, 4.1, 7.1, 7.2, 7.3
Purpose – data utility	The data from these tests can be used for battery state estimation, RUL prediction, accelerated battery degradation modeling, and reliability analysis. The main purpose of dataset is to increase the TRL of the developed models and algorithms. Moreover will the dataset help to apply the developed models to different cell types or setups to see the diversity and adaptability. The dataset will act as early input, before the data from the MARBEL cells is fully recorded, leading to many results. Finally more data will improve the overall performance of the developed solutions and will make it more robust.
File format	.csv, .mat
Data sharing plan	open
Expected size	depending on the kind of data (aging, standard cycling etc.) between 0 - 1GB approx.

Data set name	Toyota Research Institute: Data-driven prediction of battery cycle life before capacity degradation
Dataset description	This dataset consists of 124 commercial lithium-ion batteries cycled to failure under fast-charging conditions.
Data source	https://data.mtr.io/1/projects/5c48dd2bc625d700019f3204
Relevant Task	Tasks 3.1, 4.1, 7.1, 7.2, 7.3
Purpose – data utility	The objective of this work is to optimize fast charging for lithium-ion batteries. As such, all cells in this dataset are charged with a one-step or two-step fast-charging policy. The main purpose of dataset is to increase

	the TRL of the developed models and algorithms. Moreover will the dataset help to apply the developed models to different cell types or setups to see the diversity and adaptability. The dataset will act as early input, before the data from the MARBEL cells is fully recorded, leading to many results. Finally more data will improve the overall performance of the developed solutions and will make it more robust.
File format	.csv, .mat
Data sharing plan	Open
Expected size	1GB approximately

Data set name	Toyota Research Institute: Closed-loop optimization of extreme fast charging for batteries using machine learning
Dataset description	This dataset consists of 124 commercial lithium-ion batteries cycled to failure under fast-charging conditions.
Data source	https://data.matr.io/1/projects/5d80e633f405260001c0b60a
Relevant Task	Tasks 3.1, 4.1, 7.1, 7.2, 7.3
Purpose – data utility	The objective of this work is to optimize fast charging for lithium-ion batteries. As such, all cells in this dataset are charged with a one-step or two-step fast-charging policy. The main purpose of dataset is to increase the TRL of the developed models and algorithms. Moreover will the dataset help to apply the developed models to different cell types or setups to see the diversity and adaptability. The dataset will act as early input, before the data from the MARBEL cells is fully recorded, leading to many results. Finally more data will improve the overall performance of the developed solutions and will make it more robust.
File format	.csv, .mat
Data sharing plan	open
Expected size	19 GB

Data set name	Long-Term Degradation Dataset
Dataset description	The dataset consists of commercial 18650 cells cycled to 80% capacity (although cycling is still ongoing).
Data source	https://www.batteryarchive.org/sn1_study.html
Relevant Task	Tasks 3.1, 4.1, 7.1, 7.2, 7.3
Purpose – data utility	This study examines the influence of temperature, depth of discharge (DOD), and discharge current on the long-term degradation of the commercial cells. The main purpose of dataset is to increase the TRL of the developed models and algorithms. Moreover will the dataset help to apply the developed models to different cell types or setups to see the diversity and adaptability. The dataset will act as early input, before the data from the MARBEL cells is fully recorded, leading to many results. Finally more data will improve the overall performance of the developed solutions and will make it more robust.
File format	.csv, .mat
Data sharing plan	open
Expected size	2.88 GB

Data set name	Automotive Li-ion Cell Usage Dataset
Dataset description	The data set has been collected autonomously by means of a self-developed programmable battery cyler that emulates the use of electrochemical cells in the realistic environment of a pure EV. Therefore, the data has been collected by simulating the use of a lithium polymer cell model in an electric car. In order to consider a realistic environment, car trips have been composed by mixing urban, extra-urban and highway driving cycles with rests and battery charging phases.
Data source	https://iee-dataport.org/documents/automotive-li-ion-cell-usage-data-set
Relevant Task	Tasks 3.1, 4.1, 7.1, 7.2, 7.3
Purpose – data utility	The enclosed data set aims at providing a generic and realistic use of electrochemical cells upon which it will be possible to test and validate novel models and the related system identification procedures. The main purpose of dataset is to increase the TRL of the developed models and algorithms. Moreover will the dataset help to apply the developed models to different cell types or setups to see the diversity and adaptability. The dataset will act as early input, before the data from the MARBEL cells is fully recorded, leading to many results. Finally more data will improve the overall performance of the developed solutions and will make it more robust.
File format	.csv, .mat
Data sharing plan	open
Expected size	1.22 GB

Data set name	Secondary Life Cycle Inventory (LCI)
Dataset description	This dataset will contain inventory of input and output flows for the battery pack system. Such flows will include inputs of water, energy, and raw materials, and releases to air, land, and water. The inventory will based on literature analysis.
Data source	The dataset originates from well-established LCA datasets (ecoinvent, ILCD, etc.), technical documents, scientific publications, etc. It may be combined with the primary LCI.
Relevant Task	Tasks 8.1,8.2,8.3
Purpose – data utility	The main purpose of the dataset is to determine the economic and environmental impact in all life cycle stages of the solutions in order to improve LCA by using modularity, ecodesign of battery packs and flexible BMS and thus, to meet the circular economy goals. The dataset will feed into the impact model in order to demonstrate how these objectives are accomplished.
File format	Mainly *.xlsx
Data sharing plan	Open
Expected size	2 datasets (economic and environmental) <= 5 MB

Data set name	Secondary Economic assessment
Dataset description	This dataset contains data regarding the life cycle costs, including the whole battery pack system (modules and cells pack, housing, control modules and BMS,..) (raw materials and production of the components and their assembly), operational costs, end of life (recycling, disassembling,...) costs

Data source	When primary economic assessment data is not available, secondary data will be used from literature sources or available cost tools (e.g. BaTPac from Argonne Institute).
Relevant Task	Tasks 8.2, 8.3, 8.4
Expected to become available	At the end of the project
Purpose – data utility	The main purpose of the dataset is to provide information about the costs of the batteries and to contribute to the time/cost reduction at all levels, from battery pack design to dismantling and reconditioning processes. This dataset will allow the comparison of the MARBEL battery economic performance with current LIB and demonstrate the cost reduction of the MARBEL's design.
File format	.xml
Data sharing plan	To be defined
Expected size	<< 100Mb

3. FAIR DATA

3.1 Findable data and provisions for metadata

Digital Object Identifiers (DOI) will be requested for MARBEL data artefacts, in order to make them findable. In more details, DOIs from Crossref will be used for research publications, while DOIs from DataCite (<https://datacite.org/>) will be pursued for uniquely identifying each dataset of the project. In addition, a metadata record for each output of the project will be created and stored in the data directory. Amongst other fields, each metadata record will have a set of keywords that will make searches easier for external parties.

3.1.1 Naming Convention Strategy

Each data source will be provided with a specific name that will be composed by different parts/elements, containing information about pilot country, data type or format and naming structure as follows:

ORG_TOD_FORMAT_Info_VERSION

- **ORG**: The initials for the company providing the data
- **TOD**: The type of data
- **FORMAT**: The data format/extension
- **Info**: Additional (abbreviated) information about the dataset. For example, in the case of battery tests, a DATE field can be used for specifying the date that the test was performed.
- **VERSION**: The version of the dataset.

3.1.2 Version Numbering Strategy

A data versioning strategy similar to software versioning will be followed by applying a two-part numbering rule: Major.Minor (e.g. V1.1). Major data revision indicates a change in the formation and/or content of a dataset that may bring changes in scope, context or intended use. For example, a major revision may increase or decrease the statistical power of a collection, require change of data access interfaces, or enable or disable answering of more or less research questions. A Major revision may incorporate:

- substantial new data items added to /deleted from a collection
- data values changed because temporal and/or spatial baseline changes
- additional data attributes introduced
- changes in a data generation model
- format of data items changed
- major changes in upstream datasets.

Minor revisions often involve quality improvement over existing data items. These changes may not affect the scope or intended use of initial collection. A Minor revision may include:

- renaming of data attribute
- correction of errors in existing data
- re-running a data generation model with adjustment of some parameters
- minor changes in upstream datasets.

3.1.3 Metadata & Search keywords

All datasets that will be openly available will be accompanied with metadata information in order to render them findable by interested third parties. A set of search keywords will be provided and will be part of the related metadata for each dataset.

At this point we plan to use the CERIF <https://www.eurocris.org/cerif/main-features-cerif> metadata format. However, in the course of the project we will check and identify any other applicable formats.

3.1.4 Openly accessible data

A number of datasets that will be used for the purposes of project are offered by previous studies. Some of these datasets are already open to the public, while others are proprietary and have high commercial sensitivity. In the cases where private data are processed and aggregated (e.g. as part of a model, or functionality of a component) permission will be requested by the provider prior to making the altered data publicly available.

In reference to the nature of the user data involved, some of the results that will be generated by each project phase will be restricted to authorised users, while other results will be publicly available. Data access and sharing activities will be rigorously implemented in compliance with the privacy and data collection rules and regulations, as they are applied nationally and in the EU.

Datasets characterised as “openly accessible” will be published in OpenAire:

<https://www.openaire.eu>.

3.1.5 Scientific Publications

As required by the Grant Agreement, the project partners are committed to make available research publications through Green Open Access where possible. Open access publications will be made available at the MARBEL and Institutional portals. If applicable, Gold Open Access may be necessary, where the publication will be openly available through the publisher’s website. The publications of the project will be disseminated through the project’s dissemination and exploitation channels and follow the process described in the relevant project strategies.

3.2 Source code

It will be at the discretion of individual consortium members to decide whether the source code of their developed software is openly accessible. In such cases, different free and open-source software licenses will be investigated and the appropriate one will be selected. Open source code from the MARBEL project will be made available through a source code repository such as GitHub or GitLab.

Since the DMP is expected to mature during the project, the subsequent releases of the deliverable will specify the repositories where the data will be stored and go into more detail on how this data can be accessed by the wider research community.

3.3 Data Interoperability

MARBEL partners will use metadata vocabularies when possible, to render the provided datasets interoperable. The formats that will be used will be described in later versions of the data management plan.

4. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

As far as the resources related to data management planning activities are concerned, a dedicated task, Task 1.3 Data Requirements, planning and management, has been defined, in which all the project's partners participate. In total, 10 person-months of effort have been allocated to the relevant task. In addition, €20.000 have been allocated for the generation of Open Access publications. The task is led by ICCS who together with all the partners will handle the management of data related to the technological aspects of the platform.

5. DATA SECURITY AND PROTECTION

The MARBEL BMS and AI driven cloud platform and Human Machine Interfaces, will provide all required measures for secure data management and access with the usage of the latest encryption tools and protocols as well data access control practices to prevent misuse or data manipulation. The data security mechanisms will be defined and implemented as part of task 4.3 Communications and Sensors. It is envisaged that the starting candidates will be TLSv3 protocol for secure data connections and OAuth for access control.

5.1 Storage of sensitive data

In cases where sensitive data will be stored, data privacy and data protection issues will strictly follow the "user decides" principle. End-users will always have the possibility (and only the user) to decide which personal or private data to be used. Moreover, if user related data need to be published or referenced, these will always be grouped and combined via anonymization tools to avoid the possibility of breaking it down to one user. Additionally, any personal data stored within the MARBEL project will be archived for the lifetime of the project only, and will be coded, stored and kept in a secure location and all data will be protected by password access. No information will be shared with any external to the MARBEL consortium party without the prior express permission of the user.

Moreover specific provisions have been put in place for data collected through the MARBEL website and privacy as well as cookie policies have been provided (also available in ANNEX II and ANNEX III).

5.2 Adherence to the General Data Protection Regulation

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (Regulation (EU) 2016/679)¹ concerns issues related to the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (GDPR). The regulation has been proposed and established by which the European Parliament, the Council of the European Union (EU) and the European Commission. It intends to strengthen and unify data protection for all individuals within the EU and addresses issue related to the export of personal data outside the EU. GDPR aims primarily to give control to citizens and residents over their personal data and to simplify the regulatory environment for international business by unifying the regulation within the EU. GDPR has been adopted on 27 April 2016, while it became enforceable from 25 May 2018, allowing a two-year transition period for member states.

The MARBEL project does not expect to collect personal data. However, the consortium will ensure that in cases where user and personal data are gathered from the project as well as related process adhere to GDPR. More specifically we have focused on twelve main steps which have been proposed by the ICO organization (Information Commissioner's Office) in the UK² as follows.

Step 1: Awareness. All partner organizations, corresponding decision makers and key persons within the MARBEL consortium have been informed of the GDPR enforcement and have been provided with related material in order to understand the impact of GDPR in their work.

Step 2: Information held. The consortium, starting from this deliverable, will be documenting any personal data that will be held along with information related to where these data came from and with whom they will be shared with. Records of data processing activities will be maintained. The aforementioned actions will allow the consortium to comply with the GDPR's accountability

¹ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32016R0679>.

² <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-the-general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr>.

principle, which requires organisations to be able to show how they comply with the data protection principles, for example by having effective policies and procedures in place.

Step 3: Communicating privacy information. The MARBEL plan for providing privacy notices will consider the GDPR guidelines. End-users will be informed of the lawful basis for processing the data, the data retention period and that they have a right to complain to MARBEL if they think there is a problem with the way we are handling their data. All related information will be communicated to end-users in concise, easy to understand and clear language.

Step 4: Individuals' rights. The MARBEL consortium will provide procedures to cover all the rights individuals have, including how personal data are deleted as well as provide data electronically and in a commonly used format. More specifically, the following rights for individuals are considered: the right to be informed; the right of access; the right to rectification; the right to erasure; the right to restrict processing; the right to data portability; the right to object; and the right not to be subject to automated decision-making including profiling.

Step 5: Subject access requests. Handling data access requests in MARBEL considers the following points: i) No charging will apply for complying with a request. Data access requests will be handled within a maximum period of one month. The project will refuse that are manifestly unfounded or excessive. ii) If a request is refused, a clear justification will be provided and which will also inform the individual of the right to complain to the supervisory authority and to a judicial remedy. Any justification will be provided within a maximum period of one month.

Step 6: Lawful basis for processing personal data. A lawful basis for data processing activities has been established and relies on informed consent and privacy notices.

Step 7: Consent. The informed consent forms which will be provided to end-users will comply and meet the GDPR standard. The consent will be freely given, specific, informed and unambiguous. Moreover, it will be separate from other terms and conditions, and will provide simple ways for users to withdraw consent.

Step 8: Children. Although we do not expect underage pilot participants, the age of the users will be verified and parental or guardian consent for any data processing activity will be obtained for underage users.

Step 9: Data breaches. MARBEL establishes procedures to detect, report and investigate a personal data breach. Where a breach is likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of individuals, these individuals will be notified directly.

Step 10: Data Protection by Design and Data Protection Impact Assessments. MARBEL will follow a privacy by design approach.

Step 11: Data Protection Officers. The responsibility for data protection compliance and falls under the Data Protection Officers of the partners involved in volunteers' recruitment and sensitive data handling, who have the knowledge, support and authority to ensure that the project, its procedures and outcomes adhere to GDPR.

6. ETHICAL ASPECTS

The MARBEL project consortium has long and extensive experience in the conduct of ethically sound research in compliance with national legislation, EU legislation, respect for international conventions and declarations, and their own institutional requirements. The overall responsibility for ethical governance of the project will rest within the Project Coordinator, and concerning data management to the appointed Data Manager (ICCS). The research will be carried out in accordance with the ethics and data protection legislation of the participating countries, European legislation, and international conventions, as well as international declarations and codes of conduct relevant to research activities which include:

- Committee of Ministers Council of Europe (1990). Recommendation (No. R(90)3).
- Conventions of the Council of Europe (Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the
- Universal Declaration of UNESCO (Universal Declaration on the and Human Rights, 11 November 1997).
- Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU (signed in Nice, December 7, 2000, 2000/C364/01).
- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (GDPR)

Note that MARBEL involves Third countries. Turkey and Norway are Non-EU consortium members and project materials and data will be exchanged between the partners throughout the project duration. The participants ASAS and SINTEF, from Turkey and Norway respectively, confirm that the ethical standards and guidelines of Horizon2020 will be rigorously applied. Deliverable 10.4 is presenting the procedures that will be implemented for assuring the compliance with ethics-related Article 19 of Regulation (EU) N° 1291/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013 establishing Horizon 2020 and the Article 34 of the MARBEL Grant Agreement (Ethics and Research Integrity).

6.1 Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)

IPR will receive special attention from the beginning. All rules regarding management of knowledge and IPR will be governed by the Consortium Agreement (CA). MARBEL will be initially based on DESCA (CA Model) H2020 model for the CA. MARBEL will not act in contradiction with the rules laid down in Annex II of the Grant Agreement. The CA will address background and foreground knowledge, ownership, protected third party components of the products, and protection, use and dissemination of results and access rights. In this regards, the following principles will be applied:

- Confidentiality: During the project duration and beyond, the contractors shall treat any information, which is designated as property by the disclosing contractors, as confidential. They also shall impose the same obligations to their employees and suppliers.
- Pre-existing know how: Each Contractor is and remains the sole owner of its IPR over its pre-existing know-how. The Contractors will identify and list the pre-existing know-how over which they may grant access rights for the project. The Contractors agree that the access rights to the pre-existing know-how needed for carrying out their own work under the project shall be granted on a royalty-free basis.
- Ownership and protection of knowledge: The ownership of the knowledge developed within the project will be governed by an open source license.

- Open data: Data and results obtained during the project that are based on open public-sector data will be made available free of charge.

The procedures for the dissemination, protection and exploitation of IPR are covered in the CA (including sections 9.8.2 General principles and 9.8.3 Access to Software). IPR will be applied according to the rules of the employer under the applicable European and national laws and regulations.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The DMP presented in the preceding sections outlined the practices that the MARBEL consortium will follow in order to manage data and publications to be used, or to result from the project. This live document will be updated during the project. Related updates will be included in the periodic reports and in Deliverable D1.3 “Project quality and data management report” (M42).

In this version of the deliverable we have described the different types of data that we envisage to collect, their sources, the purposes for collecting such data and our planned activities for fair usage of the MARBEL data by the research community. In addition, we have discussed data security and ethical considerations, as well as the resources available for managing data as part of the project.

8. ANNEX I: Dataset Registration Form

MARBEL Data Management Plan - Dataset Registration

As part of Task 1.3 "Data requirements, planning and management", we need to gather datasets that the MARBEL project will be using and generating.

The following form is used to capture the datasets details.

Registered datasets will be reported in deliverable D1.2: Data management plan.

We ask you to register already available data that you may be using for the purposes of MARBEL, and data that are expected to be generated within the duration of MARBEL.

Please fill in the form once per dataset.

Relevant partner

Add your name, your organization and email, we may contact you in case of questions

Your answer _____

Data set name

Add a descriptive short name for the dataset

Your answer _____

Dataset description

Examples could be: - Dataset from BMS functionality: voltage and temperature limits, sensor failures, balancing; -Dataset from battery testing including standard cycling, charge/discharge, capacity validation, pulse-power-test, peak power test, cranking power etc.. provide as many details as possible.

Your answer

Dataset type: primary or secondary?

Primary data: new data collected in the duration of the MARBEL project e.g., Data from BMS, test data from lab experiments ----- Secondary data: already existing data relevant to MARBEL e.g., datasets that can be found in open databases, already available test data from the lab.

- Primary
- Secondary

Data source

Briefly describe where do the data come from, for example: are these data from experimental test procedures (from a cycler, from lab)? from testing at the eVIL level? open data from a published paper? etc.. In case of existing datasets include a URL (if available) / details on how the data can be accessed (if possible).

Your answer

If the data are generated from a test procedure please describe the relevant test here

e.g., tests in order to heat/cool the battery, fast charging

Your answer

Work Package / Relevant Task

Add here the work package number where the data will be generated and the relevant task number, e.g. WP7 - Task 7.3

Your answer

If it's a new dataset, when will it be available? If it's an existing dataset when was it collected?

e.g., 2022; after the MARBEL pilot,

Your answer

What is the purpose of data collection/generation? "Data utility": to whom this dataset will be useful?

e.g., training of battery management model, implementing an ECM model, etc...

Your answer

Relation to project Objective(s) - for which objective(s) is this dataset relevant?

- S01 Increase the TRL (Technology Readiness Level) of MARBEL novel concepts to TRL 7-8
- S02 Reduce >20.6% the weight of battery pack systems ensuring all required safety and performance targets
- S03 Increase useful battery life of batteries to minimum of 300,000 km
- S04 Facilitate reparability and 2nd life transition with easy and safe disassembly automatization
- S05 Develop solutions adaptable to all kinds of cells, electro-chemistries, vehicles, automotive segments, OEMs
- S06 Reduce 25 % the charging time of battery packs and increase fast-charging repetitiveness
- S07 Develop sensors, secure communications and enhance predictive maintenance
- S08 Increase the MRL (Manufacturing Readiness Level) of new battery pack concepts by allowing large scale manufacturing, assembly, dismantling, safety and reconditioning by design
- S09 Ensure time/cost reduction at all levels, from battery pack design to dismantling and reconditioning processes
- S010 Meet circular economy goals by minimum 40% Life Cycle Analysis improvement by using modularity, ecodesign of battery packs and flexible BMS, thus reducing environmental impact in all life cycle stages
- S011 Retrieve European industrial and social leadership at battery pack by becoming the future market standard

Why is the dataset relevant to the selected objectives?

Add a short rationale

Your answer

Format / related standards / metadata

Provide details on the format (e.g. csv / xml / json etc.) and the data model (e.g. a snippet or the attributes), related standards if available, related metadata descriptions - provides any standards that could be relevant for the dataset

Your answer

What is the Data sharing plan? If open, please describe how it will be made available (e.g. submission to a repository?)

Examples: closed / open / licensed etc.. - MARBEL has opted for the Open Research Data Pilot which means that it would be good to produce open datasets

Your answer

Size / expected size (use a measurement unit that makes sense for the dataset)

If you know the size please add here, e.g. ~100MB or data from ~100 tests / if you do not know the size please provide an estimate.

Your answer

Submit

9. ANNEX II: MARBEL Website privacy policy

Who is the data controller for your personal data?

Data controller: FUNDACIÓ EURECAT ("EURECAT")

Tax ID number: G66210345

Address: Parc Tecnològic del Vallès. Avinguda Universitat Autònoma, 23 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès

Email address: legal@eurecat.org

Telephone: +34 93 238 14 00

Data protection delegate contact: dpo@eurecat.org

For what purpose will be processed your personal data?

Your personal data received through the contact form will be processed for the purpose of managing your query or request. However, the data collected as the result of the cookies installation, will be used for collecting statistical information on the browsing of users and improve the website based on their browsing habits. You may consult further information about the cookies purposes and its data treatment at the Cookies Policy.

On our website, there may be several forms that collect your personal data for specific purposes. In those cases, you will be previously informed about the specific data treatment information to each case, and your specific consent shall be sought.

Is it mandatory to provide all the information requested in the forms on the website?

The user must complete the fields marked as "required". Failure to complete the required personal information or to partially do so may mean that Fundació Eurecat cannot meet your requests and, consequently, Fundació Eurecat will be exempt from any liability for the non-provision or incomplete provision of the requested services.

The personal data provided by the User to Fundació Eurecat must be up to date so that the information in our records is current and without errors. The user will be liable for the veracity of the data provided.

How long will your personal data be retained for?

The personal data obtained, will be kept for the duration of the purposes for which it was collected for and its erasure is not requested, and consent is not revoked. The personal data, also, will be kept, in any case, during the legal term applicable.

What is the lawful basis for us to process your personal data?

The lawful basis for the processing of your data is the consent provided through acceptance of the data processing clause.

What recipients will your data be shared with?

The Personal data received through the forms of the website may be shared with members of the project for the exclusive purpose of managing your query or request and be able to send you the latest news about the project through periodic newsletters. You may consult the list of members [here](#).

The personal data may be shared to third-parties whose develop services to the Data Controller, those ones who has access to the personal data will not treat the personal data for their own or different purposes and they will not sold or rent them.

The personal data will not be passed on to any other third-parties, unless there is a legal obligation to do so.

What are your rights regarding your personal data?

The user may exercise their right to access their personal data, to request the rectification of inaccurate data and, where applicable, to request the data to be erased if it is no longer necessary for the purposes for which it was collected. The user may also exercise their right to data portability and to the restriction of or opposition to the processing of their data, in certain circumstances and for reasons related to their specific situation.

The user also has the right to revoke their consent at any time, without any retroactive effect on the processing of their personal data carried out until that point.

The user may exercise the aforementioned rights, under the terms provided for in current legislation, at the registered office of Fundació Eurecat or request to do so by sending an email to legal@eurecat.org.

Should the user not receive a satisfactory response, and should they wish to make a complaint or obtain more information on any of these rights, they may contact the Spanish Data Protection Agency (www.agpd.es – C/ Jorge Juan, 6, Madrid).

Automated decisions

The personal data shall not be submitted to automated decisions.

The personal data may be processed to create profiles according to the cookies that has been consented to installed by the user.

International data transfers

The personal data shall not be submitted to international transfers out of the EU. However, the Data Controller may have several suppliers that develop services out of the UE, in those cases, Fundació Eurecat shall assure that the personal data shall be treat with the legal requirements through agreement that may include standard contractual clauses or privacy certification.

What security measures has the institution implemented?

Fundació Eurecat declares that it has implemented the necessary technical and organisational security measures that guarantee the security of the User's personal data and avoid its alteration, loss, processing and/or unauthorised access considering the state of technology, the nature of the stored data and the risks to which it is exposed, whether from human action or from the physical or natural environment, in accordance with the provisions of current regulations.

Social media

MARBEL, a project coordinated by Fundació Eurecat has a profile on Twitter for publishing and disseminating information about the services provided through the website, interacting with users and acting as a customer service and social interaction channel.

The following are links to the privacy policies of the social networks on which MARBEL has an active profile:

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/en/privacy>

10. ANNEX III: MARBEL Website cookies policy

What are cookies and what are they used for?

A cookie is a file that is downloaded to the user's device when they access certain websites which stores and retrieves information about the browsing activity on their computer.

Cookies allow this website, among other things, to store and retrieve information about the user's decisions and habits. Some of the cookies used on this website are necessary for it to function.

It is important to highlight that the use of cookies does not provide access to the user's personal data.

What kind of cookies exist?

Depending on the time they remain active, Cookies can be divided into session or persistent cookies.

Session cookies are designed to collect and store data while the user accesses a website and are removed as soon the explorer is closed. They are normally used to store information which only needs to be kept in order to provide the service requested by the user on just one occasion.

Persistent cookies remain stored on the device and can be accessed and handled during a period specified by the user of the cookie, which may be from a few minutes to several years.

Additionally, depending on the organisation managing them, cookies may be classified as first-party or third-party cookies.

First-party cookies are sent to the user's device from a computer or domain managed by the website publisher and are used to provide the service requested by the user.

Third-party cookies are sent to the user's device from a computer or domain that is not managed by the website publisher, but by another organisation that handles data obtained from the cookies.

In terms of their purpose, the types of cookies are:

Technical cookies: Technical cookies allow the user to browse a website, platform or application and use the different service options found there.

Profiling cookies: Profiling cookies allow the user to access the service with some predefined general features based on a series of criteria on the user's device such as language, settings, etc.

Analytical cookies: Analytical cookies allow the website owner to track and analyse user behaviour on the websites to which they are linked. The information collected is used to measure activity on the websites and to create users' browsing profiles, with the aim of introducing improvements.

Advertising cookies: Advertising cookies allow the advertising spaces which the publisher puts on the website to be managed as efficiently as possible.

What kind of cookies does the website use?

The user may be consult and set up the website cookies managed by the website publisher at Cookie settings.

The user should take account that although the cookies may be set up, certain cookies are needed and must be installed to ensure the proper access and use of the website, this cookies does not require the user's agreed neither its management.

How do you disable cookies in a browser?

The cookies set up is directly reflected to the browser used, however here are additional information about how the user can adjust the settings in their browser so as not to accept the use of cookies, in which case the user would not have a customized browsing experience. Choosing this setting may result in certain parts of the website not being accessible, as this may cause less effective browsing.

Most browsers currently allow the user to choose whether they want to accept cookies and which types. These settings are usually found in the “settings” or “preferences” in your browser’s menu.

Depending of the browser used by the user and its functionalities used may suppose the installation of cookies that are considered as a Third-party cookies. For example, in case of user chooses Google’s browser and uses its translate tool of the full website, Google install its own cookies in the user’s computers which are not managed by the website publisher as well as has not liability about them. The settings of the browser cookies should be done by the user directly at the browser website.